

Coordination of β -Isonitroso-Imine Ligands

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COORDINATION compounds of β -isonitroso-imine ligands are known for quite sometime¹. Several attempts have been made to assign the structure of bis(isonitrosoacetylacetonimine)Ni(II) on the assumption that both the ligands have the same mode of coordination¹⁻⁴. The first recognition that each of the ligands has a different mode of coordination was made around 1970 by two groups of workers⁵⁻⁶. They suggested structure I with one of the ligands(IAI) coordinating through the nitrogens of the imino and isonitroso groups, and the other ligand(IAI') coordinating through the isonitroso oxygen and imino nitrogen. The structure in the case of the (N-methylisonitrosoacetylacetonimine) (isonitrosoacetylacetonimine)Ni(II), Ni(me-IAI) (IAI'), has been later proved by X-ray diffraction⁷. Since then a large number of nickel(II) and palladium(II) complexes of β -isonitroso-imine ligands have been prepared. In the present review an attempt is made to discuss the structures of these complexes. A list of the complexes whose structures have been elucidated is given in Table I.

TABLE I—ISONITROSO-IMINE COMPLEXES OF Ni(II) AND Pd(II)*

Ni(IAI)(IAI')
Ni(R-IAI)(IAI')
R=CH ₃ , C ₂ H ₅ , n-C ₃ H ₇ , i-C ₃ H ₇ , n-C ₄ H ₉ or n-C ₆ H ₁₁
Pd(IAI)(IAI')
Pd(R-IAI) ₂
R=CH ₃ , C ₂ H ₅ , n-C ₃ H ₇ or n-C ₄ H ₉

*Here IAI(IAI') and R-IAI represent the anions of isonitrosoacetylacetonimine (4-imino-2, 3-pentanedione-3-oxime) and its N-alkyl derivative; IEI(IEI') and R-IEI represent the anions of isonitrosoethylacetoacetateimine (1-ethoxycarbonyl-2-imino-1-propanone oxime) and its N-alkyl derivative respectively. IMI and R-IMI represent the anions of isonitrosoethylmethylketimine (3-imino-2-butanone-2-oxime) and its N-alkyl derivative. The abbreviation with dashes denote the O-coordinated ligands.

Pd(R-IAI)(IAI')

R=i-C₃H₇, C₆H₁₁, C₆H₅ or *p*-CH₃C₆H₄

Ni(IEI)(IEI')

Ni(R-IEI)(IEI')

R=CH₃, C₂H₅, n-C₃H₇, n-C₄H₉ or C₂H₄OH

Ni(IMI)₂

Pd(IMI)₂

Pd(R-IMI)₂

R=CH₃, C₂H₅, n-C₃H₇ or n-C₄H₉

Ni(R-IMI)(IAI')

R=CH₃, C₂H₅ or n-C₃H₇

Ni(R-IAI)(IEI') and Ni(R-IEI)(IAI')

R=CH₃, C₂H₅, n-C₃H₇ or C₂H₄OH.

The present complexes have square-planar structure and are diamagnetic. They may be classified into two categories: (1) asymmetrical complexes with one ligand coordinating through the oxygen and the other through the nitrogen of the isonitroso groups and (2) symmetrical complexes with both the ligands having N-coordinated isonitroso groups.

$Ni(IAI)(IAI')$, $Ni(IEI)(IEI')$, $Ni(R-IAI)(IAI')$,
 $Ni(R-IEI)(IEI')$ and $Pd(IAI)(IAI')$.

The structure in the case of $Ni(IAI)(IAI')$ is based chiefly on ir and pmr evidences^{6,7}. In the chloroform solution, the complex shows two NH stretching frequencies at 3365 and 3225 cm^{-1} . It shows further two bands at 1697 and 1672 cm^{-1} , which can be assigned to two carbonyl groups*. On the basis of these evidences the compound is suggested to have structure I.

Such a structure is supported by the presence of two NH proton and four CH_3 proton signals, two of which occur as doublets due to coupling with the the NH protons.

The structure of $Ni(IEI)(IEI')$ is also based on similar evidences.⁵ It gives⁸ two NH stretching frequencies at 3375 and 3220 cm^{-1} and two carbonyl bands at 1715 and 1700(sh) cm^{-1} . The pmr spectrum shows two sets of CH_3 , OCH_2CH_3 and NH proton signals.

Structural assignment in the case of $Ni(R-IAI)(IAI')(II)$ is based on x-ray diffraction studies⁷ as well as on the close similarity of their ir, electronic and pmr spectra^{9,10} to those of $Ni(IAI)(IAI')$. These compounds show one NH frequency around 3180 and two Carbonyl bands around 1695 and 1673 cm^{-1} .

II
 $Ni(R-IAI)(IAI')$

The structure of $Ni(R-IEI)(IEI')$ is essentially the same as that of $Ni(IEI)(IEI')$ with an imine NH proton of IEI replaced by an alkyl group⁸.

As $Pd(IAI)(IAI')$ has its mull in spectrum closely similar to that of $Ni(IAI)(IAI')$, it is suggested to have a structure similar to that of the nickel(II) complex.⁹ But in contrast to $Ni(IAI)(IAI')$, the

* Unless otherwise stated, the ir band positions quoted are in chloroform solution.

palladium complex is suggested to rearrange to a symmetrical structure in chloroform solution. This is based on the fact that the electronic spectrum of $Pd(IAI)(IAI')$ in solution is closely similar to those of $Pd(R-IAI)_2$, which are suggested to have symmetrical structure. Because of the low solubility, the solution ir and pmr spectra of $Pd(IAI)(IAI')$ could not be recorded.

$Pd(R-IAI)_2$

These complexes were prepared by the amine-exchange reaction of $Pd(IAI)(IAI')$ with primary alkyl amines.⁹ The complexes show only one carbonyl frequency and their pmr spectra show only two signals due to the methyl groups, excluding those due to the N-alkyl substituent. On the basis of these evidences structure III is suggested for these complexes :

III

$Pd(R-IAI)(IAI')$

These complexes are formed when R is a bulky group.¹ The ir and pmr spectra of these complexes are similar to those of $Ni(R-IAI)(IAI')$ and hence they are also expected to have structure similar to the nickel (II) complexes.

$Ni(IMI)_2$, $Pd(IMI)_2$ and $Pd(R-IMI)_2$

$Ni(IMI)_2$ in mull shows only one NH stretching frequency at 3271 cm^{-1} in agreement with a symmetrical structure for this compound. On the basis of ir, electronic and pmr spectral evidences symmetrical structures with N-coordinated isonitroso groups are suggested for $Pd(IMI)_2$ and $Pd(R-IMI)_2$.¹²

$Ni(R-IMI)(IAI')$

These complexes are suggested to have structure (IV) on the basis of their ir and pmr spectra.¹³

IV

V

Ni (R-IAI) (IEI')

The ir spectra show the NH and CO bands around 3148 and 1673 cm^{-1} and these correspond to those expected for O-coordinated IAI'. It is suggested that R-IMI is coordinated through the isonitroso oxygen as IMI and N-alkyl substituted β -isonitroso-imine ligands are found to have such a mode of coordination.

Ni(R-IEI)(IAI') and *Ni(R-IAI)(IEI')* :

These isomeric mixed ligand complexes are suggested structures V and VI on the basis of their ir and pmr spectra. The ir and pmr spectra of Ni (R-IAI)(IEI') is a superposition of the ir and pmr bands of R-IAI and IEI'. Similar is the case with Ni(R-IEI)(IAI') also.¹⁴

VI

Ni (R-IEI) (IAI')

Assignment of the ir and pmr bands

Some of the significant ir band positions of the present complexes are given in Table 2. Their

TABLE 2—INFRARED SPECTRAL ASSIGNMENT OF SOME IMPORTANT BANDS OF β -ISONITROSO-IMINE COMPLEXES OF Ni(II) AND Pd(II)

Complexes	C=O stretch in mull	C=O stretch in CHCl_3	N-H stretch in mull	N-H stretch in CHCl_3
Ni(IAI)(IAI')	1680	1697	3258	3365
Ni(Me-IAI)(IAI')	1650	1672	3230 (sh)	3225
Ni(Et-IAI)(IAI')	1690	1696	3165	3190
	1662	1671		
	1692	1695	3165	3190
	1660	1673		
Pd(IAI)(IAI')	1684	—	3250	—
	1655	—	3200 (sh)	—
Pd(Me-IAI) ₂	1674	1676	—	—
Pd(Et-IAI) ₂	1692	1672	—	—
Ni(IEI)(IAI')	1720	1715	3310 (w,b)	3375 (w,b)
	1700	1700 (sh)	3179 (s)	3220 (s)
Ni(Me-IEI)(IEI')	1723	1718	3188	3180
	1698	1700 (sh)		
Ni(Et-IEI)(IEI')	1715	1718	3180	3200
	1700	1702 (sh)		
Pd(i-Pr-IAI)(IAI')	1700	—	3255	3224
	1672	—		
Pd(C ₆ H ₁₁ -IAI)(IAI')	1690 (sh)	—	3232	3224
	1672	—		
Ni(Me-IMI)(IAI')	1692	1693	3127	3148
Ni(Et-IMI)(IAI')	1680	1693	3100	3148

assignments are based on comparison of the ir spectra of these complexes.

The sharp NH stretch of Ni(IAI)(IAI') at 3365 cm^{-1} in chloroform can be assigned to the N-coordinated IAI and the weak broad band at 3225 cm^{-1} to the O-coordinated ligand.⁹ Similarly, the band of Ni(IEI)(IEI') at 3375(s) and 3220 (w, b) cm^{-1} can be assigned to N and O-coordinated ligands⁸ respectively. Only the lower frequency bands are present in their respective monoalkyl derivatives.

Factors affecting the ambidentate coordination

It has been found that the amine-exchange reaction of Ni(IAI)(IAI') with primary alkylamines gives Ni(R-IAI)(IAI') without any structural change (eq. 1)⁹. This reaction is reversible.¹⁵

But when Pd(IAI)(IAI') is reacted with a primary amine, both the ligands undergo amine-exchange and the complex undergoes a rearrangement to give Pd(R-IAI)₂ with a symmetrical structure(III).⁹

The non-reactivity of IAI', in Ni(IAI)(IAI') is suggested to be due to the projecting N-O group cis to the imine group of IAI', sterically preventing the reaction. Due to the larger ionic radius of palladium(II), such steric hindrance does not become significant when R is a primary alkyl group.⁹

If this explanation is correct, one should expect Ni(IMI)₂ not to undergo amine-exchange and Pd(IMI)₂ to undergo amine-exchange. As in Ni(IMI)₂, both the ligands are N-coordinated and hence the projecting N-O groups cis to the imine groups should prevent such a reaction. This has been found to be true.

If the alkylamines involved are bulky, steric effects can become significant in the case of palladium(II) complexes also. Thus, one can expect the formation of Pd(R-IAI)(IAI'), similar to the case of the nickel (II) complexes. This has been proved to be so by the preparation of Pd(R-IAI)(IAI') when R=i-Pr, cyclohexyl, etc.¹¹

It is steric hindrance and not electronic effects that prevent the formation of Ni(R-IMI)₂ with N-coordinated ligands, is further indicated by the preparation of Ni(R-IMI)(IAI') with N-alkyl

substituted IMI. Here, as expected, the IAI' is coordinated through the isonitroso oxygen.¹³

It has been found that isonitrosoacetylacetoneimine and isonitrosoethylacetoacetateimine can coordinate through the nitrogen or the oxygen of the isonitroso group, while IMI coordinates only through the isonitroso nitrogen. It has also been noticed that N-alkyl substituted isonitroso-imine ligands always coordinate through the nitrogen.

The above behaviour probably indicates the electronic effects of the substituents. The only difference between IMI and IAI or IEI is in the substituent on the $>\text{C}=\text{N}-\text{O}^-$ carbon. IMI has an electron donating methyl group while IAI and IEI have an electron withdrawing acetyl and ethoxy carbonyl groups respectively. The Hammett σ values of methyl, acetyl and ethoxy carbonyl groups are -0.170, +0.502 and +0.450 respectively. Thus an electron withdrawing group appears to favour the coordination of the isonitroso group of isonitroso-imine ligands through oxygen or nitrogen while N-coordination with an electron donating substituent.^{8,13}

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